

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF GENDER DIFFERENCES IN LANGUAGE IN SHAPING AN EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION PROCESS

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Abstract:

This article discusses about the distinctive features of language use between genders to create effective communication process. In society people always need to communicate with each other for several purposes and it is not always effective or as they expected. There number of verbal and nonverbal factors that are highly influential to form successful communication atmosphere. Linguistic elements, way of understandings and response approaches that people may not consider about during or before the interactions. Or nonverbal clues such as body language, facial expressions, and gesture. This article reveals all this necessary aspects and shares researchers view on the matters. The same with nonverbal clues linguistic elements of language are also different between men and women, including vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation or even tone of voice. As long as communication is an indispensable part of our lives we need to learn all necessary aspects that are crucial to organize an effective interaction activity.

Key words: gender differences in language, communication process, students, nonverbal clues, communication.

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Introduction part:

Gender differences in language use is one of the significant matters to investigate to create effective communication process. Gender may significantly impact on communication process considering individuals style, preferences and expectations. Man and women show different communication patterns due to social atmosphere they live and societal norms. Many researches show that men often demonstrate a communication style that is based on directness and put a focus on a task while women put an emphasis on emotions and social relationships. Sometimes, these differences leads to misunderstandings and difficulties in collaboration. Understanding gender differences in language use can considerably influences in shaping an effective communication process.

By analyzing gender effects to the language we can reveal all influential factors that gives a rise to a better understanding of communication atmosphere. And it is not only about distinctive areas but also analyses of various factors to form these particular interaction methods. There several aspects including grammar, pronunciation, word choice and sentence structure from the language side and

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behavioral elements (nonverbal clues) we may find rather distinctive in each aspect when we speak about variations between men and woman speech.

The discussion area of this article is differences in communication style between genders. Particularly, linguistic features (generally language they use: vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation aspects), attitude towards different situations (response reactions) and elements to shape their communication approaches. In many instances, people aren't capable of understanding each other in social atmosphere for this reason they may fail to create an effective communication process. By disclosing several prospects concerning this matter we can meticulously analyze speech patterns and address main problems that pose to misunderstandings. Since this is one of the frequent problems that appears in social interactions and people still find it challenging to understand each other and in most cases they end up with low consequences. If people are aware of approaching correctly and accordingly they may generate successful communication performance.

Literature Review

From research, it has been proven that men and women speak about 16,000 words in a day but in different ways, that's why John Gray argues that men are from Mars, women are from Venus. The term "gender communication style" describes the way in which man and women communicate differently, encompassing variations in language use, nonverbal and verbal conduct, societal standards. Men interrupt more frequently than women do, while women use more nonverbal clues than men do. There are just examples of common variances. People can display any communication style, regardless of gender, therefore these distinctions are not always distinctive.

However, it doesn't seem like people know why there is a difference. They sometimes reinforce preconceptions or concentrate on obvious problems rather than delving deeper into the reasons behind the different ways that the genders behave. Here some differences between men's and women's communication way are pointed by Nageenizhar:

1. Language: The language used by men and women in communication can differ in several ways, including:

Vocabulary: Women may use more emotional words and more tentative language, while men may use more direct and confident language.

Tone: Women tend to use a higher-pitched, more expressive tone of voice, while men tend to have a deeper, more assertive tone.

Volume: Men are often more likely to speak loudly, while women tend to speak more softly.

Pronouns: Women tend to use more inclusive language, such as "we" and "us," while men tend to use more individualistic language, such as "I" and "me."

2. Verbal behavior:

Interruptions: Men are often more likely to interrupt, while women are more likely to allow others to finish speaking.

Assertiveness: Society often expects men to be more assertive in communication, while women are expected to be more passive.

Confidence: Men tend to speak with more confidence, while women tend to be more hesitant and apologetic.

Emotionality: Women are often more likely to express emotions and feelings in their speech, while men tend to avoid emotional expression.

Directness: Men tend to be more direct in their communication, while women may be more indirect and use more indirect language.

Non verbal cues: Nonverbal cues such as body language, facial expressions, and gestures can vary between men and women in communication. Some differences include:

- Men tend to use more dominant body language, such as taking up more space, standing tall, and spreading their arms. Women may use more nurturing gestures, like touching and pointing toward others.

- Men may use less expressive facial cues, such as avoiding eye contact, while women may use more eye contact, smiles, and other emotional cues to express empathy.

- Women tend to use more touch in communication, such as a hug or a pat on the back, while men tend to use less touch in their interactions.

Additionally, we can see from practical observations woman mostly use complex or long sentence structure while man try to be more simple and short. Woman use emotive and descriptive language to express themselves and expressions showing politeness such as “Would you like? or can you?”. Tentative language showing uncertainty: “It seems; probably” they are also common for mostly women’s” options whereas man go directly and concretely. But still, it’s important to note that these are general tendencies and not absolute rules and that individuals may vary in their use of nonverbal cues based on their culture, personality, and individual experiences.

Discussion:

Many researchers expressed their view on this matter and discussed from different side. We talked about linguistic aspects mostly but we can see variations in their interaction preferences, interested areas that we need to disclose these areas also if we want to achieve and understand communication.

“Men will talk about sports, money, or business... things outside of themselves. Women will talk more about each other, or themselves. If an opportunity arises for small talk in the office, and a woman discloses something about herself, the man may find himself asking “Why is she telling me this?” (Kelli Wharton, 2015). Men generally avoid small talks because they think conversation should be used to share information. They simple lack experience in the art of “chit –chat”. Boys typically participate in group activities as they are growing up, while girl prefer to play in smaller groups or one on one settings. Educationally, men have over the years dominated the science fields while women take hold of the art subjects. Documented literature reveals that men in most cases perform better than women in mathematics, chemistry and physics. Women on the other hand do better than men in languages, literary works and social sciences. As a result, men often take a practical approach towards issues and life while women take an expressive approach to the same. This would to some extent explain why women are better communicators than men. In addition, it justifies why men use more gestures, assumes that there is a different solution to a problem and finds it hard to admit when they are wrong. Women on the other hand are able to express themselves eloquently and communicate towards conflict resolution and avoidance. When it comes to persuasion, males are more persuasive in their communication when compared to women. For instance, it is

nature for male to persuade women when initiating and intimacy relationship. This kind of persuasive is socially and culturally accepted. But there are occasions where women are good persuaders especially when they are talking on emotional topics such as child abuse or violence. When discussing g on these topics, they vary their tone and choose words selectively which triggers emotional instinct swaying people to buy their ideas. On the other hand, men are not good persuaders on certain topics such as emotional topic that are associated with society and issues to do with child abuse or sex abuse as they are not easily aroused by the emotions. Women are more open and express more often more in private places as they are able to share their problems. On the other hand, male like to express in the public places as this demonstrates their capability and is seen as a sign of power. Simma Liberman argues that in non-verbal behavior women will nod their head to show that they are listening. Men leave the conversation thinking that a head nod means agreement and will be surprised to find out that the woman didn't agree at all. When a woman is speaking to a man and he does not say anything and stays in neutral body language to show that he is listening, a woman will interpret that as the man being bored or not understanding what she is saying. This can lead the woman to become very uncomfortable and repeat what she is saying or ask the man each time if he understands what she is saying. The man then interprets that as insecurity, or talking to much and which then lead him to think she is not assertive or confident to be a leader. Women will actually use more direct eye contact in conversation to create relationship and connection while many men take that as a challenge to their power or position. Women will also approach a man from the front while men often approach from the side at an angle, which is how each of them tends to stand or sit when talking to others. Men interpret the face to face as too personal, or aggressive and women will interpret the talking side to side as though he is not being upfront or even hiding something from her.

Results:

An effective communication plays crucial role in every aspect of life. Individuals can learn from each other. When communicating with women, men can easily learn openness, sensitivity and self-control with competitiveness while women can learn to be assertive, more direct and mirror their feelings when engaging in conversation with male. Therefore, these differences exhibited by these genders are understood by both the genders, communication can be enhanced and barriers to effective communication and understanding can easily be managed. Regardless of different situations, marriage, business, management, awareness of gender differences in communication can prove successful in working with teams, presenting your services or products, managing conflicts and even in improving management of groups. Furthermore, identifying these differences in gender communication can help couples and people in general in identifying behaviors and traits that are exhibited by their partners and in themselves. This will therefore, help in balancing their differences and appreciating each other in term of their communication patterns. Acknowledging these differences is not necessarily trying to change them as it is very difficult to change these social and genetic solutions, but trying to adapt to them and empathize with them even to a little magnitude can lead to a more rewarding relationship between these men and women.

Conclusion:

Generally, gender communication is pivotal to the peaceful and harmonious coexistence among individuals. Not only does this type of communication promote equality among the sexes, it also presents them with an opportunity to learn, adapt and respect each other's differences in mannerisms, thought processes and preferences. From this report, it is evident that the gender communication differences are influenced by stereotypic tendencies exhibited by human beings. But it is also possible different results as well because of mostly outer factors that are connected with our surroundings.

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